

Surface Properties of Some Indian Vermiculites and Chlorites

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Adsorption, desorption and chemisorption of the polar organic liquid and the basic cationic dye on some homoionic clay minerals—vermiculites and chlorites—are reported. The limitations of measurement of specific surface based on these measurements are discussed.

SEVERAL important properties of clay minerals e.g., adsorption, shrinkage, ion exchange capacity, plasticity etc. are dependent on the specific surface areas^{2,10}. Methods for surface area measurements by gas adsorption are very tedious and require sophisticated instruments. Other simple and convenient methods, which may be applied to measure the specific surface areas of clay minerals are (i) retention of polar organic liquid like ethylene glycol and (ii) adsorption of a basic dye like methylene blue. Attempts have been made by different workers to evaluate the specific surface areas of clay minerals using glycol retention value^{2,4,8,12,13}. Adsorption characteristics of cationic dyes on the clay surfaces to determine the specific surface areas have been proposed by many investigators^{1-3,5,6,9,10,16}.

The object of the present investigation is to study and compare the glycol retention and dye adsorption characteristics of some Indian vermiculite and chlorite minerals of different origin and to correlate the results of the findings with the cation exchange capacities and structural compositions of the minerals.

Materials and Methods :

Materials : The clay samples taken in this study are (A) vermiculites from Bagespura (Karnataka), Malavangatta (Karnataka) and Ranchi (Bihar), and (B) chlorites from Kulu (Himachal Pradesh) and Nainital (Uttar Pradesh)¹⁴. These samples were collected from regions of different climatic zones as well as different geological setting and rock types of India.

Methods : Clay fractions ($<2 \mu$) were isolated from powdered natural samples by the usual process of dispersion and sedimentation¹⁵ and converted into homoionic H-form by passing through ion exchange resin (Amberlite IR-120 H-form). The base exchange capacity (b.e.c.) values of these clays were determined by the standard procedures¹¹.

The glycol retention values of the clay fractions were measured by the method of Dyal and Hendricks⁹ and the specific surface areas were

calculated from adsorption data. The external surfaces were determined from the glycol retention of the samples previously heated to 600° for 1 hr. The difference between the total and external surfaces gave the internal surfaces.

The adsorption of methylene blue by the H-clays was carried out according to the procedure stated earlier³ and the specific surface areas were calculated from the dye adsorption values.

Results and Discussion

The results are summarised in the Table. In vermiculite samples, the total surface area, as calculated from the glycol retention values, decreases with the heat treatment indicating a reduction in sorption which is approximately 80% in the Bagespura H-clay, 66% in the Malavangatta H-clay, and 55% in the Ranchi H-clay. Adsorption is thus on both external and internal sites and the internal surfaces of the vermiculites are more than the corresponding external surfaces. The abnormal lower values compared to the reported results are considered to be due to (i) low exchange capacity of the sample (cf. Table), (ii) higher tetrahedral substitution (as revealed from chemical analyses, substitutions are 31.1, 27.7 and 16.7% in Bagespura, Malavangatta and Ranchi vermiculites respectively) and (iii) low K_2O content^{2,4,12,13}. It is reported that lower glycol retention in minerals is due to Al substitution in the tetrahedral layer and glycol can not replace K ions, which are held by stronger forces¹². It may be noticed that the external surface areas of these vermiculites are more or less the same in all the minerals but their internal surfaces differ to a great extent. The degree of interstratification (cf. hydrobiotite) plays an important role for surface area measurements. The Bagespura sample having vermiculite as major constituent¹² with less interstratification shows higher internal surface area as compared to that of the Malavangatta sample where transformation to interstratified mineral is more². In the Ranchi sample, the vermiculisation process has not taken

TABLE—SURFACE AREA AND C.E.C VALUES OF H-CLAYS

Clay samples	Total glycol retention (mg/gm)	External glycol retention (mg/g)	K ₂ O %	Total surface (m ² /g)	External surface (m ² /g)	Internal surface (m ² /g)	c.e.c. by KCl/NaOH (meq/100 g)	c.e.c. from dye adsorption maximum (meq/100 g)	Surface area (m ² /g) from dye adsorption
A. Vermiculites									
(i) Bagespura H-clay	9.89	2.76	2.20	31.9	8.9	23.0	78.0	10.5	22.23
(ii) Malavangatta H-clay	8.74	2.91	2.30	28.2	9.4	18.8	49.92	9.7	21.07
(iii) Ranchi H-clay	6.23	2.94	2.20	20.1	9.5	10.6	48.65	6.77	13.65
B. Chlorites									
(i) Kulu H-clay	5.33	3.26	2.30	17.2	10.5	6.7	15.28	3.44	7.42
(ii) Nainital H-clay	3.91	2.45	2.28	12.6	7.9	4.7	13.93	0.7	1.51

place and thus the total surface area is the lowest amongst the vermiculite minerals studied².

The glycol retention capacities of the chlorite samples are of lower order than the published values^{4,12,14}. Such low glycol retention values indicate the lower organophilic character (complexing ability with polar liquids) of chlorites. The low base exchange capacity and the presence of appreciable quantity of quartz as impurity (indicated from X-ray diffraction study) in these chlorites are considered as the cause of the low value. Another possible reason for the low glycol retention is that when glycol retention is complete, mechanical mixtures of expanded and nonexpanded layers are formed in preference to randomly interstratified layers causing an impermeable layer which prevents penetration of glycol into the interior of the surfaces resulting in low retention values¹².

Fig. 1. Adsorption and desorption curves of Malavangatta, Bagespura and Ranchi H-Clays.

●, ▲, ■—Adsorption. ○, △, □—Desorption
●-○- Malavangatta ▲-△- Bagespura ■-□- Ranchi

The results of the dye adsorption studies are shown in the Table and Figs. 1 and 2. Adsorption of dye by the homoionic H-clay from these vermiculite samples increases linearly with increase in dye concentration, showing a Freundlich's type isotherm (Fig. 1). The dye adsorbed upto saturation point (adsorption maximum) is 93 μ moles/gm in the Bagespura H-clay, 88 μ moles/g in the

Fig. 2. Adsorption and desorption curves of Kulu and Nainital H-Clays

●, ▲-Adsorption, ○, △-Desorption
▲-△- Nainital ●-○- Kulu

Malavangatta H-clay and 53 μ moles/g in the Ranchi H-clay (from curves). The surface area, as calculated from the saturation capacity, is found to be lower than that obtained from the corresponding glycol retention value. When desorbed by 10% KCl solution, a very small portion of the dye adsorbed at the surface remains fixed due to chemisorption (supported by X-ray data) and shows hysteresis in the isotherm.

The dye adsorption characteristics of the homoionic chloritic clay are similar in nature to those of vermiculite samples (Fig. 2) but the adsorption capacity of the chlorite samples is of a very low order e.g. maximum 33.0 μ moles/g in the Kulu H-clay and 6.3 μ moles/g in the Nainital H-clay. This is possibly due to the presence of quartz as impurity. It is possible to desorb most of the dye adsorbed on the clay surfaces by treatment with 15% KCl solution showing that unlike vermiculite clays weak adsorption forces are operative in this case.

Although the adsorption of dye from aqueous solution by these minerals is considered as due to exchange reaction between H ions and the dye cations, the c.e.c. values as obtained from the dye adsorption maxima are less than that obtained from KCl/NaOH method (Table). This is possibly due to the formation of a monolayer of dye before c.e.c. is satisfied and a single methylene blue cation might have covered more than one exchange site. As the dye cation volume is large, other dye cation could not come closer to replace the adjacent H ion due to steric hindrance and hence there is incomplete

replacement of exchangeable cations by dye cations^{2,14}.

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